

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART IV. PRELIMINARY INVESTIGATIONS ON FACTORS INFLUENCING RANCIDITY

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A detailed study of the different factors influencing rancidity of butterfat has been carried out. The primary agent responsible for the development of rancidity is oxygen; the effect of light, moisture and micro-organisms are merely catalytic.

The enormous losses incurred in fats and oils, oil bearing foods and similar commodities due to the development of bad odour and taste, known generally as rancidity, have engaged the attention of numerous investigators. A vast literature has accumulated on this subject but as yet no clear understanding of the complete process is available. Various theories have been advanced and much experimental evidence has been adduced to substantiate one hypothesis or another and these have often resulted in confusing rather than clarifying the problem, and considerable doubt still exists as regards the actual agent or agents responsible for causing rancidity in fats and the mechanism of the process. Oxygen, moisture, light, certain metals and micro-organisms are the various agents proposed as the causes of rancidity in fats but it has not been answered with certainty whether it is a single agent that can produce the effect or a combination of two or more of these will be absolutely necessary to develop rancidity. Some of the workers claim that moisture and air together must act simultaneously, either of these alone being unable to produce rancidity and that light and micro-organisms are of secondary importance (Godbole and Sadgopal, *Z. Lebensm.*, 1936, 72, 36); some assert that light alone in the absence of air or oxygen is capable of producing rancidity, and air and moisture are not necessary (Wagner, Walker and Oestermann, *Z. unters. Nahr-u. Genussm.*, 1913, 25, 704), while others claim that light and air are both essential to produce rancidity and that reports that exposure of fats to light alone is capable of producing rancidity *in vacuo* are erroneous (Schmalzfuss, Werner and Gührke, *Marg. Ind.*, 1935, 25, 215, 242; Täufel, Thaler and Martinez, *ibid.*, 1933, 26, 37). As regards the action of micro-organisms, there is one school who hold that these agents play no part in producing rancidity (Duclaux, *Ann. Inst. Pasteur*, 1887; *Compt. rend.*, 1886, 102, 1077), while others believe that they act as simple catalysts and are not primarily responsible for the development of rancidity (Godbole *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). It thus appears necessary to study whether one and only one factor is primarily responsible for the process, or association of one or more of these factors will be an absolute necessity for the onset of rancidity in fats.

In the ordinary process of development of rancidity in fats and oils it is sometimes very difficult to evaluate the effect of a specific environmental factor in the overall process, because in most cases several of these are simultaneously active. Of the several factors that may be operating, viz., oxygen, light, moisture, heat, micro-

organisms, etc. one may predominate under one set of conditions and quite a different one under another.

It therefore appears logical to carry out an investigation in which the effect of various environmental factors should be studied by making a careful control of the variables 'within relatively narrow limits'. In the experiments described in this paper, the effect of elimination of air, light, moisture and micro-organisms has been studied on the development of rancidity of butterfat on storage in glass vessels at 37° for a period of three months and the course of rancidity followed by determination of peroxide, Kreis and acid values. The following studies were undertaken :

- I. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air, light and moisture.
- II. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air and light (moisture only is absent).
- III. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air and moisture (light only is absent).
- IV. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of light and moisture (air only is absent).
- V. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of moisture only (both air and light are absent).
- VI. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of light only (both air and moisture are absent).
- VII. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air only (both light and moisture are absent).
- VIII. The effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air, light and moisture, without previous sterilisation and exposed to atmospheric conditions.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

In all these experiments (Groups I-VII), the effect of micro-organisms was minimised by a preliminary sterilisation of the fat and using aseptic conditions as far as practicable during handling. The temperature effect was eliminated by storage in an incubator at 37°. The moisture content was determined by the A. O. A. C. method (cf. Methods of Analysis, A.O.A.C., 6th Ed., 1945, p. 501) using distillation with toluene and was found to be 0.20% and is always the same unless otherwise mentioned. Group VIII records experiments with fat stored as such without sterilisation in presence of air, light and moisture.

Exclusion of Light.—In experiments with Group III, V and VII light was excluded by storing the butterfat in 150 c.c. conical flasks (plugged with sterilised cotton wool), covered completely with black paper and placing the whole in the incubator.

Exclusion of Moisture.—In experiments with Groups II, VI and VII moisture was excluded as follows: The fat was first of all kept for 12 hours in a liquid state in an incubator at 39-40° in contact with one-tenth its weight of anhydrous Na₂SO₄ (A.R.). The fat was then transferred to large (6" diam.) pyrex dishes which were thoroughly cleaned and dried in an air-oven at 200° for 2 days and then over a P₂O₅ desiccator in vacuum (0.1 mm.) for a period of one month. The fat was then poured in

thin layers in such dishes and kept over P_2O_5 in vacuum (0.1 mm.) for one week in the dark before the actual experiment started. During handling the fat the effect of contamination from micro-organisms was reduced by working up inside a chamber sterilised with ultraviolet light for a period of 30 minutes. The fat thus dried was believed to be in all probability perfectly free from moisture and the result was checked by determination of moisture by the A.O.A.C. method which showed no measurable amount of moisture in the fat. But having regard to Baker's work on the influence of moisture in chemical reactions and the difficulty in removing the same absolutely from glass surface, it would be very difficult to assert whether insignificant traces of moisture were not present in the samples prepared; but for all practical purposes the samples might be treated as anhydrous.

Exclusion of Air.—In experiments with Groups IV and V, Thunberg's tubes were used for storage of fats with considerable advantage. The tubes were half-filled with the fat and the standard taper ground joint stopper put in place with a thin layer of vacuum grease and the tubes evacuated by means of a Cenco high vacuum pump for 4 hours, the stop-cock was closed, and the tube filled with pure nitrogen from a cylinder (freed from any oxygen by passage through alkaline pyrogallo' and dried over $CaCl_2$) drawn through a filter of sterilised cotton wool, and evacuated again for 2 hours, refilled with pure and dry nitrogen and again evacuated for 2 hours and finally kept filled with pure and dry nitrogen in order to prevent chances of leakage. A preliminary passage of pure nitrogen gas through the fat for several minutes before evacuation in Thunberg's tube was found advantageous for completely removing the last traces of oxygen. Here also aseptic conditions were rigorously followed as far as practicable in order to prevent contamination from micro-organisms such as operations inside a sterilised chamber and use of sterilised cotton filters during the passage of gas and during sampling of fat for determination of the values, use of sterilised pipettes and working inside sterilised chamber were strictly adhered to.

The peroxide value was determined by a modified Wheeler method, already indicated in Part II, as outlined below.

About 0.1 g. of the fat is weighted into a 500 c.c. glass-stoppered iodine bottle from which air has previously been excluded by flushing with CO_2 for 3 to 5 minutes and 10 c.c. of a solvent comprising 40 parts $CHCl_3$ and 60 parts A.R. acetic acid (glacial) are added to dissolve the fat. The solvent must be flushed with CO_2 for 5-10 minutes before use to exclude any dissolved air. Saturated KI solution (2 c.c.) is next added and the stopper moistened with KI solution is put in place and the whole after thorough shaking kept in the dark for 1 hour after which the liberated iodine is titrated with 0.002*N* thiosulphate after diluting the reaction mixture with oxygen-free distilled water using 1% starch solution as the indicator. The peroxide value is expressed as the ml. of 0.002*N* thiosulphate required per g. of fat.

The acid value was determined by the usual method and expressed as percentage of free oleic acid (acid value $\times 0.5031$). The Kreis test was performed by the method of Pool and Prater (*Oil & Soap*, 1945, 22, 215). Since the procedure adopted differed in some minor detail from the original, the exact procedure is described below.

The fat (2 c.c.) is pipetted in a test tube (25 c.c.) and diluted to 5 c.c. with chloroform and treated with 5 c.c. of a 30% trichloroacetic acid in acetic acid solution and 1 c.c. of an 1% solution of phloroglucinol in glacial acetic acid. The resulting mixture is thoroughly shaken and the test tube is placed in a thermostat at $40^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ}$ and allowed to stand for exactly 15 minutes. After this time, the mixture is diluted with 5 c.c. (or 10 c.c.) of absolute alcohol and the colour matched in a Lovibond tintometer. The Kreis value has been expressed here as the number of Lovibond units per g. of fat. The analytical results are recorded in Table I (Groups I—VIII).

TABLE I
Peroxide, Kreis and acid values after

	15 days			30 days			45 days			60 days			85 days		
	*P.V.	K.	A.V.	P.V.	K.	A.V.									
Group I. Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air, light and moisture at 37°.															
Sample I	0.15	0.1	0.2	0.30	1.6	0.45	2.5	4.3	0.71	3.2	8.8	1.3	19.0	12.6	2.1
Sample II	0.14	0.1	0.2	0.30	1.6	0.43	2.4	4.2	0.70	3.2	8.4	1.3	18.8	12.4	2.0
Sample III	0.13	0.1	0.2	0.28	1.6	0.41	2.3	4.1	0.70	3.0	8.0	1.3	18.8	12.4	2.0
Mean	0.14	0.1	0.2	0.29	1.6	0.43	2.4	4.2	0.70	3.1	8.3	1.3	18.9	12.5	2.0
Group II. Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air and light at 37°.															
Sample I	0.10	0.0	0.0	0.18	1.3	0.0	1.0	2.1	0.10	1.8	3.8	0.30	8.5	6.0	0.37
Sample II	0.10	0.1	0.0	0.20	1.3	0.0	1.2	2.5	0.10	2.0	3.8	0.30	8.5	6.0	0.41
Sample III	0.10	0.0	0.0	0.21	1.4	0.0	1.0	2.5	0.15	2.0	4.0	0.31	8.5	6.0	0.43
Mean	0.10	—	0.0	0.20	1.3	0.0	1.1	2.5	0.12	1.9	3.9	0.30	8.5	6.0	0.40
Group III. Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air and moisture at 37°.															
Sample I	0.08	0.0	0.18	0.15	1.0	0.30	0.50	3.0	0.60	1.0	6.0	0.95	10.8	8.0	1.8
Sample II	0.10	0.0	0.18	0.15	1.0	0.30	0.51	3.1	0.60	2.0	6.5	0.96	10.9	8.1	1.9
Sample III	0.09	0.0	0.17	0.14	1.0	0.28	0.50	3.0	0.50	2.0	5.6	0.94	10.8	8.0	1.7
Mean	0.09	0.0	0.18	0.15	1.0	0.29	0.50	3.0	0.57	2.0	6.0	0.95	10.8	8.0	1.8
Group IV. Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of light and moisture at 37°.															
Sample I	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.11	0.0	0.0	0.20	0.0	0.0	0.71	0.10	0.1	0.95
Sample II	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.08	0.0	0.0	0.19	0.0	0.0	0.53	0.02	0.0	0.90
Sample III	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.11	0.0	0.0	0.20	0.0	0.3	0.66	0.02	0.0	0.92
Mean	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.10	0.0	0.0	0.20	0.0	0.0	0.62	0.04	—	0.92
Group V. Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of moisture alone at 37°.															
Sample I	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.02	0.0	0.0	0.19	0.0	0.0	0.90	0.00	0.0	1.10
Sample II	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.05	0.0	0.0	0.20	0.0	0.0	0.92	0.05	0.3	1.10
Sample III	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.06	0.0	0.0	0.25	0.0	0.0	0.96	0.10	0.6	1.25
Mean	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.04	0.0	0.0	0.21	0.0	0.0	0.93	0.25	0.3	1.15
Group VI. Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of light only at 37°.															
Sample I	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.16	0.0	0.0	0.20	0.02	0.1	0.40
Sample II	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.18	0.0	0.0	0.20	0.02	0.1	0.41
Sample III	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.15	0.0	0.0	0.18	0.02	0.0	0.40
Mean	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.16	0.0	0.0	0.19	0.02	0.1	0.40

TABLE I (contd.)

	15 days			30 days			45 days			60 days			85 days		
	P.V.	K.	A.V.												
Group VII. Effect of storage of butterfat in presence of air only at 37°.															
Sample I	0.08	0.0	0.0	0.15	0.1	0.0	1.1	0.8	0.05	2.0	2.4	0.20	7.5	3.3	0.11
Sample II	0.08	0.0	0.0	0.14	0.1	0.0	1.0	0.8	0.04	2.0	2.3	0.15	7.5	3.2	0.40
Sample III	0.08	0.1	0.0	0.12	0.1	0.0	1.0	0.7	0.02	2.0	2.3	0.10	7.2	3.1	0.40
Mean	0.08	—	0.0	0.14	0.1	0.0	1.0	0.8	0.05	2.0	2.3	0.15	7.4	3.2	0.40
Group VIII. Effect of storage of butterfat (in presence of air, light, moisture) without sterilisation and exposed to atmospheric condition.															
Sample I	0.15	0.1	0.2	0.20	1.0	0.50	2.0	3.0	1.2	2.8	4.6	1.50	12.0	6.9	4.2
Sample II	0.15	0.1	0.2	0.20	0.8	0.50	1.9	2.7	1.0	2.3	4.4	1.45	10.6	7.0	2.6
Sample III	0.15	0.1	0.2	0.20	0.3	0.51	2.0	2.8	1.1	2.5	4.6	1.47	11.1	7.3	4.0
Mean	0.15	0.1	0.2	0.20	0.7	0.50	2.0	2.8	1.1	2.5	4.5	1.47	11.3	7.0	3.9

* P.V. stands for peroxide value, A.V. for acid value and K for Kreis No.

Rancidity as detected by taste and smell developed quickly in experiments of Groups I and VIII within 45 days and more slowly with those in Groups II, III and VII (after 60 days), but with samples of Groups IV, V and VI there was no detectable off-flavour which was so characteristic in the control samples (Group I). These results were well corroborated by peroxide and reis Ktests. From the above table the following conclusions were drawn :

In the absence of any influence of micro-organisms, hydrolytic rancidity as measured by development of free acidity proceeds only in presence of moisture, though slight acidity develops even under conditions where moisture is not present (cf. Table I, Groups II, VI and VII), but oxidative rancidity as determined by peroxide and Kreis values is observed only where air (*i.e.* oxygen) is present (cf. Table I, Groups I, II, III and VII), exclusion of air practically stops such rancidity (cf. Table I, Groups IV, V and VI). The part played by light is only one of positive catalyst (Table I, Groups I and III) in that it causes an acceleration of the rate of the reaction, the development of peroxides is diminished to a considerable extent when this factor is absent (cf. Table I, Groups I, II and III). The development of peroxide is again greater whenever the acidity is greater; this tends to show that moisture in bringing about accelerated hydrolysis of fats provides more easily oxidisable free fatty acids (at least more active than the glycerides themselves) resulting in an increased peroxide value (cf. Table I, Groups I, II, III and IV). In Group VII oxygen in absence of moisture and light fails to bring about as much rancidity as it can when moisture is present (Group III). The Kreis figures are generally in keeping with peroxide figures.

When the samples are exposed to atmospheric conditions and subject to contamination from micro-organisms (Group VIII), the peculiarity is that an acceleration in the rate of hydrolysis is noticed in the samples accompanied by a much less amount of peroxide. All these samples responded to Taufel-Thaler reaction for ketones (negative with Groups I-VII) at the end of the experiments. The behaviour of micro-organisms

has been separately studied elsewhere, but from the experiments described here it may be said that rancidity in butterfat can be developed without these agencies, and such organisms cannot be the primary causes of rancidity

One thing of particular interest is that once a certain peroxide level is reached (approximately 2.0), the rate of oxidation is increased remarkably; this therefore definitely indicates the termination of the induction period of the fat.

C O N C L U S I O N S

The fundamental and primary cause of rancidity in fats is the action of oxygen or air.

The function of light and moisture in the development of rancidity is merely catalytic, and rancidity can as well develop in the absence of such environmental factors. The action of moisture is primarily to cause hydrolysis of the glycerides. But rancidity may develop in fats by oxidation of the latter without undergoing a previous hydrolysis. As regards the relative efficiency of light and moisture in developing rancidity and off-flavour, it is very difficult to differentiate between them and state which is more prominent than the other. Fats keep better in the absence of moisture or light than in presence of it.

Micro-organisms are not primarily responsible for the onset of rancidity in fats but they play an important part in such degradation reactions and give positive evidence of a new type of rancidity characterised by increased hydrolysis and ketone formation.

In subsequent papers, the effect of the various factors such as temperature, oxygen concentration, light intensity, metallic catalysts and other chemical accelerators on the autoxidation has been studied in much greater detail.

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